

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

АНАЛИЗ СТРУКТУРЫ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ УЧИТЕЛЯ ИНФОРМАТИКИ

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ANALYSIS OF THE STRUCTURE OF PROFESSIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE TEACHERS

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена анализу компонентов профессионально-педагогической компетентности учителя информатики в контексте быстро меняющегося информационного общества. Роль учителей информатики становится ключевой в подготовке учащихся к современным вызовам, и в этой связи выделяется восемь основных компетенций: предметная, методическая, социально-психологическая, коммуникативная, цифровая, компетенции саморазвития и профессионального роста, креативная и оценочная компетенции. Также подчеркивается важность развития всех этих компонентов для успешной педагогической деятельности и обеспечения качественного образования в цифровом обществе.

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the analysis of the components of the professional and pedagogical competence of a computer science teacher in the context of a rapidly changing information society. The role of computer science teachers is becoming key in preparing students for modern challenges, and in this regard, eight main competencies are identified: subject, methodological, socio-psychological, communicative, digital, self-development and professional growth competencies, creative and evaluative competencies. The importance of developing all these components for successful teaching activities and ensuring quality education in a digital society is also emphasized.

Ключевые слова: Профессионально-педагогическая компетентность, учитель информатики, компоненты профессиональной компетентности.

Keywords: Professional pedagogical competence, computer science teacher, components of professional competence.

Introduction

Modern education is at the center of rapid technological and sociocultural development, which gives particular importance to the role of computer science teachers. These teachers are responsible for developing not only technical skills, but also a whole range of competencies necessary for successful adaptation to modern digital society. The professional and pedagogical competence of a computer science teacher is becoming a key factor in ensuring effective learning and successfully preparing students for the future.

The ICT sector plays a vital role in various aspects of public life. In a world where digital technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data, the Internet of Things and the cloud are rapidly changing our reality, computer science teachers are becoming key agents in preparing younger generations for the modern digital age. Their role is not limited to simply transferring knowledge; they are also responsible for developing

their students' skills in analysis, critical thinking, problem solving, communication and creativity.

Today's computer science teachers must address the diverse needs and abilities of their students, provide personalized learning experiences, and promote digital literacy and ethical use of information and digital technologies. All this requires them to possess a wide range of professional and pedagogical competencies.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the components of the professional and pedagogical competence of a computer science teacher, to determine their role and importance in the educational process. This research is aimed at identifying and describing the key competencies required for a computer science teacher in the context of modern education.

Literature review

2.1. Concept of competence and competency

Interest in the problem of competencies arose in the late 1960s due to the fact that assessing students' performance only by the amount of reproducible

knowledge did not allow them to fully determine their readiness to work independently and apply this knowledge in practice. Therefore, the issue of competencies has become relevant in the field of education.

An analysis of works on the issue of competence and competency allows us to conditionally identify three stages in the development of competency-based education:

The first stage (1960-1970) is characterized by the introduction of the concepts of “competence” and “competency”. During this period, attention to competence and competency in education began to grow. Assessing students' performance solely on the basis of knowledge turned out to be insufficient to determine their readiness to solve practical problems and perform independent activities. The concepts of “competence” and “competency” have become important for identifying not only knowledge, but also skills and abilities.

The second stage (1970-1990) represents a deeper introduction of the competency-based approach into educational programs, where competencies become central elements of learning. Educational programs began to focus on the development of student competencies, and not just on the transfer of factual knowledge. This reorientation of education was a response to changing needs in the labor market and society as a whole.

The third stage is characterized by the introduction of the concept of “professional competence”. At this stage, attention was paid to a narrower aspect of competence - professional competence. This concept reflects the specific skills and knowledge required in a particular professional field. The introduction of the concept of “professional competence” was an important step in the development of education, as it emphasizes not only general competencies, but also specialized skills necessary for successful professional activity.

These stages in the development of competency-based education emphasize the importance of developing student competencies in the context of modern challenges and needs of society.

2.2. The concept and structural components of professional and pedagogical competence of a computer science teacher

The professional and pedagogical competence of a teacher is a key aspect of his professional training and successful activities in the educational field. It is a set of knowledge, skills, beliefs and values that enable a teacher to interact effectively with students and provide quality education.

The concept of “professional competence of a teacher” has become the object of research in many scientific studies. Researchers such as Zimnyaya I.A. [7] and Tatur Yu.G. [4], consider the professional competence of a teacher as the most important characteristic that determines his readiness to teach and includes a variety of competencies

Professional competence of a teacher is the knowledge, ability and readiness to professionally solve practical problems in teaching and developing the student's personality and developing his practical skills [1].

The monograph “Development of Professional Competence of a Teacher” reveals the theoretical and practical aspects of the development of professional competence of a teacher [3].

In the research by Zakirova M.R. [8,9] emphasize that for a competent teacher it is not enough just to have information literacy and the ability to develop appropriate information skills in his students. It is important that a competent teacher promotes the use of information and communication technologies among students for the purpose of successful cooperation, solving current problems, and developing self-learning skills.

In the research by Kruchinina G.A. and Akimova I.V. The professional competence of future computer science teachers is considered as a generalized characteristic that is formed on the basis of practical experience in this field. This competence reflects a set of knowledge and skills, as well as the ability for self-development and solving new professional problems. Researchers identify three components in the structure of a computer science teacher's professional competence: subject-matter, methodological, and components related to information and communication technologies (ICT) [2].

From March 1, 2021, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, in order to improve the system of retraining and advanced training for managers, specialists and teaching staff operating in the field of public education, a new system of retraining and advanced training has been introduced based on a study of the needs of public education workers for advanced training and through the introduction of special electronic platform [5]. To ensure a more effective and convenient learning process and advanced training, a special electronic platform “Continuing Professional Education” has been introduced, which provides the opportunity for public education workers to study the necessary courses online.

To improve the qualifications of teachers, specific competencies necessary for the effective performance of professional duties have been identified:

- Communicative competence;
- Information and communication technologies and media literacy;
- Self-development and professional development competencies;
- Responsibility and flexibility;
- Issues on the implementation of inclusive education;
- Knowledge of regulatory legal acts and issues of using their professional activities;
- Science news and current issues in science teaching;
- Methods and means of assessing student competencies.

Based on an analysis of research in the field of professional pedagogical competence of a teacher, it can be argued that this concept is a complex and multifaceted characteristic that includes many aspects.

Modern education requires teachers not only to effectively transfer knowledge, but also to develop students as competent and independent individuals. There-

fore, the development of teacher professional competence remains a relevant and important task for educational institutions, teachers and researchers

3. 3. Research methodology

The research of the structural components of the professional and pedagogical competence of a computer science teacher is based on an analysis of literary sources. This research method allows you to systematize and generalize knowledge and previous research in this area. As part of the research methodology, scientific publications, articles, monographs, and researches on the professional and pedagogical competence of computer science teachers were analyzed.

The literature analysis included the study of various points of view and approaches to determining the competence of a computer science teacher, highlighting the key components of this competence, as well as consideration of current research results and practical aspects of professional training of computer science teachers..

4. Results and discussion

Based on the results of the study of professional and pedagogical competencies of teachers, it was revealed that they include the following basic competencies:

- Subject competence;
- Methodological competence;
- Socio-psychological competence;
- Communicative competence;
- Digital competence;
- Self-development and professional development competencies;
- Creative competence;
- Evaluation competence.

These competencies form an important basis for teacher development and improving the quality of education in general. Subject knowledge, for example, plays a key role in effectively communicating information to students, but it cannot be isolated from the teaching skills that help teachers structure the learning process. Social-psychological skills, including the ability to interact with a diverse student population, are also critical to successful teaching.

Digital literacy and the ability to adapt to change are becoming increasingly relevant in today's world, where information technology plays an important role in education. These competencies allow teachers to effectively use modern educational technologies and provide quality teaching.

Research also highlights the importance of self-development and learning abilities. The rapidly changing educational environment requires teachers to constantly update their knowledge and skills, as well as the ability to adapt to new requirements.

Creative competence and evaluative competence allow computer science teachers to attract students' attention and evaluate their progress. Effective assessment of students' knowledge and skills is an integral part of the educational process. Computer science teachers need to know how to properly assess students' progress and provide feedback to them.

This analysis highlights the versatility and importance of computer science teacher competencies.

Today's educational demands and the impact of digital technologies make these competencies essential to delivering quality learning and preparing students for a digital future. Educational institutions and teacher preparation programs must actively work to develop and strengthen these competencies in education and training.

5. Conclusions

This article analyzed the components of the professional and pedagogical competence of a computer science teacher. The results of the analysis allow us to draw the following conclusions:

– The professional and pedagogical competence of a computer science teacher is a complex and multifaceted set of competencies necessary for the successful education of students in a modern digital society.

– The concept of professional pedagogical competence has evolved over time, starting with a narrower understanding as a set of subject knowledge and methodological skills, and expanding to include socio-psychological aspects, creative competencies, etc. In addition, the modern understanding of teacher competence takes into account the importance of meta-competencies.

– Each of the eight identified competencies (subject-specific, methodological, socio-psychological, communicative, digital, self-development and professional growth competencies, creative and evaluative competencies) plays an important role in the formation of the professional readiness of a computer science teacher.

– Subject competence requires deep knowledge of computer science, methodological competence includes the ability to teach the subject effectively, socio-psychological competence helps in managing the classroom and maintaining psychological comfort, and communicative competence contributes to effective communication. Digital competence and abilities for self-development and professional growth are especially important in the context of an ever-changing information environment.

– Creative competence and evaluative competence allow computer science teachers to attract the attention of students and evaluate their progress.

Based on the results of the analysis, we can conclude that the training of computer science teachers should pay special attention to the development and strengthening of these competencies. This will help ensure high quality education and student readiness for a digital future. Competent computer science teachers play an important role in creating an educated and technologically literate generation that can successfully adapt to a rapidly changing world.

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